

Distributed Agentic AI Framework for Autonomous Edge-Cloud Service Orchestration

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ABSTRACT Orchestrating services across heterogeneous 6G edge-cloud infrastructures requires autonomous coordination systems managing distributed computational resources while satisfying Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirements. Recent advances in Large Language Models (LLMs) enable development of autonomous agents capable of complex reasoning and decision-making for such orchestration tasks. However, applying generic agentic AI frameworks from the machine learning literature to orchestration domains introduces reliability limitations, as trial-and-error decision patterns are unsuitable for environments where errors disrupt services. This work presents AgentEdge, a novel distributed intelligence framework that implements specialized autonomous agents in four orchestration roles: intent processing, infrastructure monitoring, strategic planning, and action execution. AgentEdge introduces the PARES (Perceive, Act, Reason, Evaluate, Sustain) framework establishing minimum capabilities required for autonomous agent qualification. Central to AgentEdge is the ActSimCrit (Action-Simulation-Critic) planning methodology, which validates orchestration plans through digital twin simulation before execution, eliminating direct infrastructure experimentation risks. Agents coordinate multi-step operations and adapt strategies based on constraint feedback. Structured outputs constrain agent decision spaces to feasible orchestration actions while preserving optimization flexibility. Experimental evaluation in six orchestration scenarios validates AgentEdge through comparison with baseline agentic frameworks and ablation studies. AgentEdge achieves $2.76\times$ higher success rate compared to generic agentic frameworks (ReAct, LATS) and $10\times$ reduction in API call variability. The core ActSimCrit digital twin component alone contributes $1.47\times$ success improvement when compared to direct planning without simulation. AgentEdge achieves significant power savings across infrastructure scales from 8 to 35 nodes.

INDEX TERMS Agentic AI; Large language models (LLM); Multi-agent systems; Generative AI; Edge computing; 6G networks; Cloud orchestration; Digital twin; Autonomous systems; Service orchestration

I. INTRODUCTION

MODERN sixth-generation (6G) networks demand orchestration systems capable of managing many distributed nodes under strict latency and quality-of-service (QoS) requirements [1], [2]. Cloud-native architectures have reshaped the deployment of services throughout the compute continuum, requiring seamless coordination of thousands of microservices distributed over far-edge devices, near-edge nodes, and cloud data centers. Traditional centralized orchestration platforms do not meet these demands. They introduce unaccept-

able delays through sequential decision-making bottlenecks and create single points of failure that cascade across distributed 6G infrastructures [3].

To address these limitations, Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches have evolved from classical machine learning (ML) methods to Large Language Models (LLMs). LLMs demonstrate the ability to interpret complex user requirements and reason about multi-constraint optimization scenarios [4], [5]. Autonomous agents built on LLM foundations combine Natural Language Processing (NLP) with goal-directed behavior for

specialized orchestration tasks [6]. Multi-agent systems extend this by distributing intelligence among collaborative specialists, each maintaining domain expertise in specific orchestration areas [1], [7], offering key advantages through parallel decision-making and specialized task optimization.

Recent research has explored both LLM-based and agent-based orchestration approaches. LLM-based systems focus on intent processing and automated configuration management [2], [8]. Agent-based approaches target domain-specific applications including wireless network management [9], [10], multi-agent coordination frameworks [11]–[13], and infrastructure orchestration [14], [15]. However, existing systems are still designed for generic domains or centralized cloud infrastructures. They do not address the specific requirements of distributed edge-cloud service orchestration [16]. A key challenge remains: operators express requirements in natural language, yet orchestration systems need precise specifications to act upon. This represents a fundamental gap in 6G edge-cloud orchestration.

Specifically, such orchestration must simultaneously address multiple unique challenges specific to the 6G environment [17], [18]: (i) heterogeneous computational resources that span resource-constrained edge devices to powerful cloud data centers, (ii) dynamic network topologies with fluctuating connectivity and variable latencies, (iii) sub-millisecond latency constraints for real-time applications, (iv) intermittent connectivity that requires autonomous decision-making capabilities, (v) energy optimization across distributed nodes with varying power consumption profiles, and (vi) geographic distribution necessitating coordinated control across the compute continuum.

Agentic AI approaches originally designed for other domains are characterized by trial-and-error learning and direct experimentation [6], [19]. Such exploratory methods raise reliability concerns for 6G deployments where services have strict QoS requirements and failures cascade across distributed infrastructure. Any QoS violation may lead to severe consequences, making these approaches unacceptable for edge-cloud orchestration.

To address these fundamental limitations, this article introduces AgentEdge¹, a novel multi-agent orchestration framework that represents a paradigm shift from centralized to distributed intelligence approaches for edge-cloud environments. AgentEdge enables operators to express intent naturally (e.g., “deploy with low latency”) and translates these requests into validated orchestration actions.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We provide a detailed presentation of the first multi-agent system for 6G edge-cloud service orchestration, translating natural language intent into validated actions through structured workflows across heterogeneous infrastructure.
- We introduce the PARES framework (Perceive, Act, Reason, Evaluate, and Sustain), which defines minimum agent capabilities for quantitative agentic behavior characterization.
- We establish the Action-Simulation-Critic (ActSim-Crit) methodology that integrates comprehensive digital twin simulation into agent decision-making, enabling risk-free validation of orchestration strategies before real-world execution.
- We systematically evaluate five state-of-the-art open-source LLMs for 6G orchestration tasks using non-fine-tuned foundation models for fair off-the-shelf comparison.
- We compare AgentEdge against baseline agentic AI frameworks widely adopted in other domains, demonstrating $2.76\times$ higher success rates and $10\times$ reduction in Application Programming Interface (API) call variability through specialized multi-agent coordination.
- We evaluate AgentEdge in energy optimization scenarios across infrastructure sizes from 8 to 35 nodes, characterizing power savings across these scales and the current planning limitation at the largest evaluated case.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work on generative AI for orchestration, Section III presents the system model and problem formulation. Section IV introduces our proposed framework (AgentEdge). Section V provides a detailed experimental evaluation. Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

This section reviews: (i) LLM-based orchestration approaches for intent processing and code generation, (ii) agent-based orchestration systems spanning domain-specific applications, multi-agent coordination, and infrastructure management, and (iii) fundamental limitations that motivate AgentEdge.

A. LLM-BASED ORCHESTRATION

LLM-based approaches divide into two primary categories: intent processing with translation and code generation with configuration management.

Intent Processing and Translation: LLM-based systems focus on natural language intent interpretation and transformation. Other studies [21] demonstrate intent extraction capabilities for 6G core networks. Advanced approaches employ a four-stage methodology to convert natural language intentions into Network Service

¹A high-level approach of our framework with preliminary proof-of-concept results has been presented in [20].

Descriptors using Code Llama LLM [2], incorporating few-shot learning, similarity-based retrieval, closed-loop validation, and human feedback for continuous improvement.

Code Generation and Configuration Management: Research focuses on automated code synthesis and network configuration deployment. Recent studies [8] present task-specific code generation for network graph analysis and manipulation, combining application-specific prompts with program synthesis techniques to address explainability, scalability, and privacy challenges. Complementary work [22] introduces a modular framework that addresses data privacy and LLM errors in router and firewall configurations.

However, current LLM-based orchestration systems face critical limitations [17], [23]. These include model errors, real-time adaptation challenges, insufficient API integration, and monolithic architectures unsuitable for distributed edge-cloud environments.

B. AGENT-BASED ORCHESTRATION

Building upon these LLM foundations, agent-based orchestration systems represent the next evolution, using autonomous AI agents for coordinated service orchestration across heterogeneous environments.

Domain-Specific Agent Approaches: Implementations target specialized networking applications with customized agent architectures. In wireless network management, researchers [9] demonstrate intelligent network management through LLM-powered agents. For fault management, other work [10] introduces an LLM-based agent system with integration of memory, knowledge base, and network infrastructure. This system autonomously manages the complete fault management cycle through proactive traffic monitoring, delay detection, and flow rerouting. For network planning applications, researchers [16] present a three-module framework with specialized tools for geographic map retrieval, environment creation, and automated radio map generation. However, these approaches rely on single-agent architectures that cannot distribute reasoning across specialized roles. They lack formal capability definitions and execute actions directly without pre-validation in a simulated environment.

Agent Coordination and Collaboration: Moving beyond single-agent approaches, researchers have developed frameworks for multi-agent cooperation and coordinated decision-making. Recent work [11] employs a chain-of-agent approach that separates network modeling into specialized roles using YAML-based blueprints with mathematical formulas and pseudocode. Other approaches [12] present multi-agent systems with LLM-based agents for conflict resolution and resource negotiation on the business, service, and network planes. Additional work [13] uses agents across the application,

physical, and network layers, evaluated through industrial automation and virtual reality applications. These frameworks use flat coordination structures without hierarchical organization. LLM outputs are accepted without constraint verification, and plans are tested through trial-and-error on production infrastructure rather than simulation.

Infrastructure Orchestration and Service Management: Finally, these approaches focus on sophisticated agentic implementations for distributed service management and deployment. Recent work [14] employs machine learning models for QoS predictions and enables autonomous migration of containerized applications in Kubernetes-based edge-cloud environments. Other work [15] presents an intent-based orchestration approach employing four specialized agents with distributed coordination. This system utilizes Model-Context Protocol integration for tool standardization and employs fine-tuned Mistral-7B and Qwen3-0.6B models through QLoRA [24] for Kubernetes configuration tasks. These systems assume cloud-centric architectures with reliable high-bandwidth connectivity, limiting applicability to heterogeneous edge-cloud environments. They address deployment but not migration, scaling, or power management, and lack digital twin validation for multi-step plans.

C. FUNDAMENTAL LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT APPROACHES

Existing infrastructure orchestration and service management approaches [14], [15], [20] exhibit critical gaps for distributed edge-cloud environments. They focus on centralized cloud infrastructures, target narrow applications without addressing complete service lifecycle management, and lack formal agent capability definitions and coordination mechanisms for distributed multi-agent collaboration.

Furthermore, generic agentic approaches from the ML literature [6], [19] employ trial-and-error learning requiring direct experimentation on production infrastructure. This creates reliability concerns for deployments where failures cascade across distributed infrastructure, establishing the need for specialized multi-agent orchestration frameworks designed explicitly for edge-cloud service management.

AgentEdge addresses these limitations through PARES capability definitions enabling formal agent reasoning, ActSimCrit methodology replacing trial-and-error with digital twin validation, and graph-of-graphs architecture supporting distributed coordination. Table 1 summarizes this comparison.

Traditional optimization methods solve placement problems given formally specified objectives but cannot interpret natural language intents or handle partial infrastructure states [3]. AgentEdge operates at a higher abstraction: translating intent into constraints and in-

voking optimization methods as backends within the Planning Agent (Section IV-A).

III. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

This section presents: (i) the infrastructure model characterizing nodes and network topology, (ii) the service orchestrator interface, (iii) the service model with resource requirements and placement constraints, (iv) LLM calls with dynamic structured outputs for validation, (v) the agentic framework, (vi) the problem formulation as optimization under constraints, and (vii) orchestration challenges motivating our approach. The notation used throughout the paper is presented in Table 2.

Fig. 1 illustrates the system model components and their interactions. A user submits natural-language intent $\zeta(t)$ to the Agentic Framework \mathcal{A} , which coordinates four agent roles (Intent \rightarrow Observe \rightarrow Plan \rightarrow Act). The framework exchanges prompts \mathbf{p} and validated outputs \mathbf{z} with the LLM validation module, where dynamic schemas $\mathcal{V}_i(t)$ constrain agent outputs. The Service Orchestrator \mathcal{O} mediates between the framework and infrastructure: it receives agentic commands, translates them to Kubernetes API calls, and returns formatted state $\mathbf{u}(t)$ from API responses. Services $s_j \in \mathcal{S}$ with demands \mathbf{d}_j are placed on infrastructure nodes $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ connected by network links with latency $\ell(n_i, n_j)$. Upon completion, the framework returns a natural-language response $\rho(t)$ to the user.

A. INFRASTRUCTURE MODEL

We model the edge-cloud infrastructure as a network of computational nodes with heterogeneous capabilities spanning from resource-constrained edge devices to powerful cloud data centers.

Formally, the infrastructure topology is represented as a graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{E})$ where:

- $\mathcal{N} = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m\}$ is the set of m computational nodes
- $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N}$ represents network connectivity between nodes

Each node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ has finite resource capacity characterized by a two-dimensional vector:

$$\mathbf{r}_i = (r_i^c, r_i^m) \in \mathbb{R}_+^2, \quad (1)$$

where r_i^c denotes CPU cores and r_i^m is memory in bytes.

Resource utilization is expressed as normalized fractions, where current utilization observed at time t is:

$$\mathbf{u}_i(t) = (u_i^c(t), u_i^m(t)) \in [0, 1]^2, \quad (2)$$

where each component represents the fraction of capacity consumed for the corresponding resource type (CPU or memory), enabling unified constraint checking and optimization across heterogeneous resource dimensions.

The communication latency between nodes n_i and n_j is denoted $\ell(n_i, n_j) \in \mathbb{R}_+$ in seconds, representing the network delay for data transmission between nodes.

Additionally, power consumption at node n_i follows a linear utilization-dependent model:

$$p_i(t) = p_i^0 + \alpha_i(w_c \cdot u_i^c(t) + w_m \cdot u_i^m(t)), \quad (3)$$

where $p_i^0 \geq 0$ is the idle power consumption in watts. The parameter $\alpha_i > 0$ is the dynamic power coefficient in watts that represents the maximum additional power draw with full utilization. The weights $w_c, w_m > 0$ are dimensionless CPU and memory utilization weights, respectively. This linear model is established for datacenter power modeling and achieves less than 1% error when validated against measured power [25].

B. SERVICE ORCHESTRATOR

The agentic framework \mathcal{A} does not interact with infrastructure nodes directly. Instead, a service orchestrator \mathcal{O} mediates between the framework and the underlying container orchestration platform (e.g., Kubernetes). Communication follows a bidirectional flow: the framework issues high-level agentic commands (e.g., “deploy service s_j to node n_i ”), which the orchestrator translates into platform-specific API calls (e.g., Kubernetes pod scheduling). The orchestrator executes these calls against the container runtime and receives API responses indicating success, failure, or resource status. These responses are then converted back into a structured format the agents can interpret, providing updated utilization state $\mathbf{u}(t)$. This architectural separation enables agents to reason about placement decisions π^* without requiring knowledge of low-level infrastructure commands, while ensuring that all infrastructure interactions occur through validated API interfaces.

C. SERVICE MODEL

Building upon the infrastructure model, the system manages a collection of services that must be placed on the infrastructure nodes while satisfying resource requirements. Services are defined as $\mathcal{S} = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{|\mathcal{S}|}\}$, where each service $s_j \in \mathcal{S}$ has resource demands:

$$\mathbf{d}_j = (d_j^c, d_j^m) \in \mathbb{R}_+^2, \quad (4)$$

where d_j^c denotes the CPU cores required and d_j^m the memory required in bytes.

Based on these service requirements, a placement is a function $\pi : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ that assigns each service to exactly one node, where we consider placement-dependent utilization $\mathbf{u}_i(\pi, t)$ representing the utilization resulting from the implementation of placement π . For placement π to be feasible, it must satisfy capacity constraints:

$$\sum_{j:\pi(s_j)=n_i} \frac{\mathbf{d}_j}{\mathbf{r}_i} \leq \mathbf{1}, \quad \forall n_i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (5)$$

TABLE 1. Comparison of Orchestration Approaches for Edge-Cloud Environments. Lifecycle: I=Intent, O=Observe, P=Plan, A=Act.

Approach	Edge	Cloud	Pre-Exec. Valid.	Lifecycle				Multi-Agent Coord.	Agent Framework
				I	O	P	A		
Intent Translation [2]	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Wireless Agent [9]	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗
Fault Agent [10]	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
Chain-of-Agent [11]	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
Multi-Agent MAS [12]	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗
Service Orch. [15]	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗
AgentEdge (Ours)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

FIGURE 1. System model overview. User submits intent $\zeta(t)$ to the Agentic Framework \mathcal{A} , which exchanges prompts \mathbf{p} and validated outputs \mathbf{z} with LLM validation. The Service Orchestrator \mathcal{O} mediates between framework and infrastructure, translating agentic commands to K8s API calls and returning formatted state $\mathbf{u}(t)$. Services s_j are placed on nodes n_i , and the framework returns response $\rho(t)$ to the user.

This ensures that the total normalized resource demands of all services placed on node n_i do not exceed unity. Vector division $\mathbf{d}_j/\mathbf{r}_i$ is performed element-wise.

D. LLM CALLS WITH STRUCTURED OUTPUTS

To enable intelligent orchestration decisions, agents leverage LLMs to process natural language input and generate orchestration decisions. Consider an agent indexed by i where the LLM interaction follows a standard input-output pattern in which the agent submits a prompt $\mathbf{p}_i(t)$ and receives a response $\mathbf{y}_i(t)$:

$$\mathbf{y}_i(t) = \text{LLM}(\mathbf{p}_i(t)), \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_i(t)$ contains the state of the system, agent observations, and task-specific instructions. The output $\mathbf{y}_i(t)$ represents the unstructured natural language response of the LLM.

However, unstructured LLM output is insufficient for reliable orchestration decisions that must satisfy strict infrastructure constraints. Therefore, our framework employs structured outputs that conform to dynamically generated schemas, enabling automatic validation and processing.

To ensure safe and constraint-sensitive operation, structured agent output is validated through dynamic schemas that adapt to the current infrastructure state and agent role. A validation schema is generated for agent i at time t :

$$\mathcal{V}_i(t) = \text{Schema}(\mathbf{u}(t), \text{role}_i), \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{u}(t) = [\mathbf{u}_1(t), \dots, \mathbf{u}_m(t)]$ is the utilization state of the system. The parameter role_i specifies the agent's designated role (e.g., intent, observe, plan, act). The schema $\mathcal{V}_i(t)$ defines the set of valid structured outputs for agent i given current conditions.

TABLE 2. Mathematical notation encompassing infrastructure topology, service placement, multi-agent system, LLM interactions, and QoS optimization

Symbol	Description	Symbol	Description
\mathcal{G}	Infrastructure graph	\mathcal{N}	Set of nodes
\mathcal{E}	Edge set	n_i	Node i
m	Number of nodes	t	Time
\mathbf{r}_i	Resource capacity	\mathbf{u}_i	Resource utilization
$\ell(n_i, n_j)$	Latency (s)	p_i	Power (W)
\mathcal{O}	Service orchestrator	$\zeta(t)$	User intent
$\rho(t)$	User response	$\text{req}(t)$	User request
\mathcal{S}	Set of services	s_j	Service j
\mathbf{d}_j	Resource demand	π	Service placement
\mathcal{A}	Set of agents	a_i	Agent i
\mathcal{R}	Set of roles	f_i	Agent function
\mathbf{T}_i	Agent tools	\mathbf{o}_i	Observations
\mathbf{p}_i	LLM prompt	\mathbf{y}_i	LLM response
\mathcal{V}_i	Validation schema	\mathbf{z}	Structured output
\mathcal{M}	QoS metrics set	h	QoS metric index
Q_h	Realized QoS value	\bar{q}_h	Target QoS value
J_{qos}	QoS penalty	γ_h	QoS metric weight
λ, μ	Trade-off weights	R, E	Load/energy costs
$\mathbf{B}^{(\tau)}$	Action batch	\mathcal{T}	State snapshots

The validation of a structured agent output \mathbf{z} against schema $\mathcal{V}_i(t)$ follows:

$$\text{Valid}(\mathbf{z}, \mathcal{V}_i(t)) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \mathbf{z} \in \mathcal{V}_i(t) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

where the structured output \mathbf{z} is accepted only if it conforms to the dynamically generated constraints. For example, consider when node n_i approaches capacity such that $\mathbf{u}_i(t) + \mathbf{d}_j/\mathbf{r}_i > \mathbf{1}$ for normalized service demand. The schema $\mathcal{V}_k(t)$ for the Planning Agent k (where $\text{role}_k = \text{plan}$) dynamically removes "deploy to n_i " from the valid action set. This prevents capacity constraint violations while preserving other actions such as migration or scaling.

The variable dependencies form a three-stage pipeline: (i) infrastructure state $\mathbf{u}(t)$ determines the validation schema $\mathcal{V}_i(t)$ via Eq. 7, constraining which actions are feasible, (ii) the LLM generates response $\mathbf{y}_i(t)$ from prompt $\mathbf{p}_i(t)$ via Eq. 6, proposing actions based on the task, and (iii) structured output \mathbf{z} is extracted from $\mathbf{y}_i(t)$ and validated against $\mathcal{V}_i(t)$. The dependency chain is $\mathbf{u}(t) \rightarrow \mathcal{V}_i(t) \rightarrow \text{constrains } \mathbf{z} \leftarrow \mathbf{y}_i(t)$, where \mathbf{z} represents the validated intersection of proposed and feasible actions.

E. AGENTIC FRAMEWORK

We now define our agentic orchestration approach, introducing the augmented LLM and multi-agent coordination mechanisms.

1) THE AUGMENTED LLM

The basic building block of our agentic system is an augmented LLM enhanced with retrieval capabilities, tools, and memory. This enables five core functions: (i) *Perceive* the state of the environment through observations $\mathbf{o}_i(t)$, (ii) *Act* through available tools \mathbf{T}_i , (iii) *Reason* through internal state \mathbf{s}_i , (iv) *Evaluate* through memory \mathbf{m}_i , and (v) *Sustain* operation over time through persistent function f_i .

Mathematically, an agent i that implements these capabilities follows the following formulation:

$$\text{output}_i = f_i(\mathbf{o}_i(t), \mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{m}_i, \mathbf{T}_i), \quad (9)$$

where the agent actively generates search queries, selects appropriate tools, and determines information retention based on orchestration requirements.

2) MULTI-AGENT COORDINATION

Extending beyond single-agent capabilities, the orchestration system employs multiple augmented LLM agents that collaboratively manage service placement through specialized roles and coordinated decision-making based on task complexity and domain expertise.

Formally, the set of agents is $\mathcal{A} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{|\mathcal{A}|}\}$, where each agent a_i has a designated role $\text{role}_i \in \mathcal{R}$. In our AgentEdge framework, we use the role set:

$$\mathcal{R} = \{\text{intent}, \text{observe}, \text{plan}, \text{act}\}, \quad (10)$$

representing intent processing, infrastructure monitoring, placement planning, and action execution, respectively.

Inter-agent communication follows structured message exchange, where agent a_i sends message msg_{ij} to agent a_j through standardized APIs.

This four-agent-type decomposition enables specialized processing while maintaining coordinated orchestration through inter-agent routing protocols.

F. PROBLEM FORMULATION

With the infrastructure, service, and agentic models established, we formulate the orchestration problem. Orchestration begins when a user expresses intent in natural language, such as "deploy service A with low latency" or "reduce energy consumption while maintaining QoS." At time t , the framework receives a trigger $\zeta(t) \in \{\text{user request}, \text{infrastructure change}\}$ as $\text{req}(t)$ and observes infrastructure state $\mathbf{u}(t)$.

The practical orchestration problem has three stages: (i) interpret the natural language request to determine which services and/or infrastructure are involved, what constraints apply, and what objective the user prioritizes, (ii) find a placement satisfying these derived constraints given current infrastructure state, and (iii) monitor the system for unexpected events or deviations from user intents. Traditional optimization methods address only

stage (ii), assuming the objective function and constraints are already formalized. AgentEdge addresses all three stages through agentic reasoning, while integrating traditional optimization techniques (heuristic or exact) as tools for placement generation by the Planning Agent. Moreover, the Planning Agent reasons over when to invoke a tool and which tool to invoke given the current orchestration scenario. The formulation below defines the problem that arises after intent translation, not the solution method.

Once intent is translated into formal constraints, placement optimization seeks a π minimizing QoS deviation and infrastructure costs:

$$\pi^*(t) = \arg \min_{\pi} J_{\text{qos}}(\pi, t; \text{req}(t)) + \lambda R(\pi, t) + \mu E(\pi, t), \quad (11)$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$ and $\mu \geq 0$ are trade-off parameters balancing QoS adherence against load balancing cost $R(\pi, t)$ and energy cost $E(\pi, t)$, respectively. The load-balancing cost and energy cost are

$$R(\pi, t) = \sum_{i=1}^m \|\mathbf{u}_i(\pi, t)\|_2^2 \quad (12)$$

and

$$E(\pi, t) = \sum_{i=1}^m p_i(\pi, t). \quad (13)$$

The optimization is subject to capacity constraints of Eq. 5 and request-specific QoS constraints

$$g(\pi, t; \text{req}(t)) \leq 0, \quad (14)$$

where $g(\cdot)$ encodes application-specific performance requirements (e.g., maximum end-to-end latency bounds, minimum throughput guarantees). We instantiate the QoS deviation as

$$J_{\text{qos}}(\pi, t; \text{req}(t)) = \sum_{h \in \mathcal{M}} \gamma_h [Q_h(\pi, t; \text{req}(t)) - \bar{q}_h(\text{req}(t))]_+, \quad (15)$$

where \mathcal{M} indexes request-level QoS metrics (e.g., end-to-end latency, success probability shortfall), Q_h is the realized metric, and \bar{q}_h is the target. The parameters $\gamma_h > 0$ are QoS metric weights, and $[x]_+ = \max\{x, 0\}$. The term $Q_h(\pi, t; \text{req}(t))$ denotes the *realized* value of QoS metric h under placement π at time t , as opposed to the target $\bar{q}_h(\text{req}(t))$ specified in the request. For latency, $Q_h(\pi, t; \text{req}(t))$ is the measured end-to-end delay while \bar{q}_h is the maximum acceptable delay. The penalty applies only when $Q_h(\pi, t; \text{req}(t))$ exceeds the target \bar{q}_h .

Additional performance or QoS constraints such as communication delay, placement region, and reliability are incorporated through user-specified natural language requests rather than hardcoded in the objective. When users specify requirements in $\text{req}(t)$, the Intent Agent parses these and the Planning Agent generates corresponding constraints $g(\pi, t; \text{req}(t)) \leq 0$. This user-centric design keeps the objective generic while allowing any parameter to be incorporated as a constraint.

For multi-objective optimization, the trade-off parameters (λ, μ) are chosen by the strategy:

$$(\lambda, \mu) = \begin{cases} (0, 0), & \text{QoS-priority mode} \\ (1, 0.1), & \text{load-balancing mode} \\ (0.1, 1), & \text{energy-optimization mode} \\ (\lambda_u, \mu_u), & \text{user-specified weights} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

The parameter pairs (λ, μ) are illustrative examples. In practice, the agentic framework determines optimal trade-off weights intrinsically based on the user's intent $\text{req}(t)$, infrastructure state $\mathbf{u}(t)$, and agent promptset. The Planning Agent reasons about these inputs to derive appropriate optimization strategy without explicit parameter specification. The examples show how intent maps to behavior: QoS-priority focuses on service quality, load-balancing distributes work evenly, and energy-optimization minimizes power.

G. ORCHESTRATION CHALLENGES

Given this optimization formulation, finding an optimal placement π^* is computationally costly for realistic problem sizes due to three fundamental challenges: i) combinatorial explosion creating a search space containing $|\mathcal{N}|^{|\mathcal{S}|}$ possible placements that grows exponentially with problem size, ii) dynamic constraints arising as infrastructure state $\mathbf{u}(t)$ changes continuously, requiring real-time adaptation of feasible placement decisions, and iii) multi-objective optimization involving competing objectives (QoS adherence, balance, and energy) that require careful trade-off analysis varying with system conditions. Traditional centralized optimization approaches cannot address these challenges simultaneously, motivating our multi-agent approach where four agent types (intent, observe, plan, and act) work together to solve Eq. 11.

IV. AGENTEDGE ARCHITECTURE

This section presents: (i) the multi-agent architecture with four specialized agents and ActSimCrit validation, (ii) the PARES capability framework for defining agent capability requirements, (iii) dynamic structured outputs constraining decision spaces, and (iv) distributed reasoning decomposition for coordination efficiency.

A. AGENTEDGE MULTI-AGENT GRAPH OF GRAPHS

Orchestration requires solving complex multi-step problems involving intent parsing, state analysis, constraint checking, and action planning. Forcing a single agent to handle all these heterogeneous tasks simultaneously degrades performance, as the agent must context-switch between fundamentally different reasoning patterns. Distributing reasoning across specialized agents improves accuracy by allowing each agent to maintain consistent focus within a specific orchestration domain. AgentEdge implements this through a hierarchical graph-of-graph architecture (Fig. 2) formalized as

FIGURE 2. AgentEdge hierarchical graph-of-graphs architecture with top-level orchestrator routing between four specialized agents, each deployed as an independent microservice implementing dedicated subgraph workflows.

$\mathcal{G}_{AgentEdge} = (G_{orch}, \{G_i\}_{i=1}^4)$. The top-level orchestrator G_{orch} routes requests between four specialized agents. Each agent implements a dedicated subgraph $G_i = (V_i, E_i, \Psi_i)$ following validation protocols from Eq. 8.

The architecture distributes reasoning across four specialized components. The *Intent Agent* transforms natural language requests into structured goals. The *Observability Agent* monitors system state. The *Planning Agent* employs ActSimCrit methodology for constraint-aware planning through digital twin simulation. The *Infrastructure Action Agent* executes validated plans through API operations. In the following sections, we provide a detailed analysis for each agent.

AgentEdge agents are implemented as independent Flask API servers, with inter-agent communication via standard HTTP requests. Placement commands are transmitted to a container orchestration platform (e.g., Kubernetes, Docker Swarm) rather than directly to computing nodes. The platform handles node-level dispatching and returns execution confirmation. The Service Orchestrator \mathcal{O} is exposed as an MCP (Model Context Protocol) server, providing agents with context for correct API parameter derivation. Agent programs are lightweight since heavy computation (LLM inference) is offloaded via API calls to external services, whether cloud-hosted LLM endpoints or on-premises GPU infrastructure. This separation enables flexible deployment: agentic code runs on minimal hardware with network connectivity, while LLM backend location becomes a deployment-time configuration choice.

1) INTENT AGENT SUBGRAPH

Autonomous orchestration systems face a semantic gap between natural language operator intentions and structured computational representations. Traditional approaches require manual translation of high-level requirements into explicit API calls. The Intent Agent converts natural language requests into structured orchestration goals through LLM-based semantic parsing, identifying services, resources, constraints, and requirements, categorizing requests among orchestration patterns with confidence scoring, and extracting operational specifications.

Formally, the intent extraction process follows the agent framework from Eq. 9:

$$\mathbf{o}_{i_{intent}}(t) = f_{i_{intent}}(\text{req}(t), \mathcal{V}_{i_{intent}}(t)), \quad (17)$$

where $\text{req}(t)$ is the user request (Table 2). The schema $\mathcal{V}_{i_{intent}}(t)$ is the validation schema from Eq. 7 for the intent agent role. The output $\mathbf{o}_{i_{intent}}(t)$ contains a structured intention specification that includes service requirements and placement constraints.

2) OBSERVABILITY AGENT SUBGRAPH

Orchestration decisions require understanding current infrastructure state, yet raw metrics alone provide insufficient context for intelligent decision-making. Agents need to detect emerging constraint violations and optimization opportunities before they impact service quality. The Observability Agent addresses this by monitoring system state $\mathbf{u}(t)$ from Eq. 2 and transforming raw metrics into actionable intelligence that identifies constraint violations and recommends preventive actions.

The workflow collects metrics through HTTP API calls retrieving system-wide and service-specific data, routes between general system analysis and focused service health assessment, and generates structured observations.

Mathematically, the monitoring process follows the agent framework. For the observe agent with index $i_{observe}$ where $\text{role}_{i_{observe}} = \text{observe}$:

$$\mathbf{o}_{i_{observe}}(t) = f_{i_{observe}}(\mathbf{u}(t), \mathcal{V}_{i_{observe}}(t)), \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{u}(t) = [\mathbf{u}_1(t), \dots, \mathbf{u}_m(t)]$ contains all node utilizations. The schema $\mathcal{V}_{i_{observe}}(t)$ is the validation schema from Eq. 7 for the observe agent role. The output $\mathbf{o}_{i_{observe}}(t)$ provides alerts and recommended actions based on detected patterns and constraint violations.

3) PLANNING AGENT SUBGRAPH WITH ACTSIMCRIT

The Planning Agent generates feasible multi-step orchestration plans using ActSimCrit methodology. The Planning Agent operates as a coordinator rather than a monolithic optimizer. It can invoke external tools, including mathematical solvers or heuristics, as optimization backends when formal optimization is beneficial.

The agent’s role is to translate intent into actionable plans, select appropriate solution methods based on problem characteristics, and validate outputs through ActSimCrit before execution. This design enables dynamic tool selection: formal solvers for tractable problems, heuristics for large-scale deployments, or LLM reasoning for novel scenarios requiring zero-shot generalization.

ActSimCrit preserves orchestration action quality by replacing trial-and-error experimentation with safe digital twin validation. The methodology maintains a synchronized digital replica of the infrastructure state \mathcal{G} from Section III, including computational nodes \mathcal{N} and network links \mathcal{E} , enabling what-if analysis before real orchestration actions.

ActSimCrit operates as a structured graph $G_{\text{planning}} = (V, E, \Psi)$ where V , E , and Ψ represent processing functions, valid transitions, and function mappings (Fig. 3). Specialized LLM reasoning nodes handle complex orchestration decisions, with an independent critic LLM (no memory sharing) ensuring unbiased evaluation. The methodology operates through five distinct phases:

- 1) **Strategic Planning:** LLM generates high-level orchestration strategies by processing natural language objectives and infrastructure constraints to establish end-goal states and constraint hierarchies.
- 2) **State Analysis:** LLM analyzes structured infrastructure data to identify constraints and optimization opportunities through mathematical constraint validation.
- 3) **Strategic Action Selection:** LLM selects action batches from options filtered by constraints. It uses the rejection context $\mathcal{X}^{(\tau)}$ to avoid previously failed combinations.
- 4) **Digital twin simulation:** A deterministic simulation validates LLM-generated action batches using $\mathbf{S}_{\text{simulated}}$. The independent critic LLM provides objective evaluation:

$$\mathbf{S}_{\text{valid}} = \{\mathbf{s} : \text{constraints}(\mathbf{s}) \wedge \text{feasible}(\mathbf{s})\}, \quad (19)$$

where constraints include capacity limits from Eq. 5 and power consumption from Eq. 3.

- 5) **Intent Satisfaction Evaluation:** LLM evaluates progress toward orchestration objectives.

Four core mechanisms enable ActSimCrit’s effectiveness: (i) strategic action batching for efficient resource coordination, (ii) three-tier state management preventing corruption during multi-step planning, (iii) rejection-feedback learning transforming failures into actionable constraints, and (iv) deadlock detection with resolution for infeasible intents. The Planning Agent with index i_{plan} where $\text{role}_{i_{\text{plan}}} = \text{plan}$ generates placement decisions

through iterative cycles:

$$\pi^{(\tau)} = f_{i_{\text{plan}}}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{o}_{i_{\text{intent}}}, \mathcal{X}^{(\tau)}), \quad (20)$$

where τ denotes the planning iteration number and $\mathcal{X}^{(\tau)}$ represents the accumulated rejection context from previous planning iterations. The digital twin simulation validates the candidate placements against Eq. 5.

a: Strategic Action Batching

Without batching, agents generate orchestration actions one at a time, introducing unnecessary planning overhead for logically connected action sequences. For example, when only one service remains on a node, the natural sequence is migrate-then-low-power, yet single-action planning requires multiple LLM calls and iterations to discover this straightforward pattern. This overhead reduces the efficiency of the planning cycle. AgentEdge addresses this through strategic action batching in which LLM reasoning generates action sequences $\mathbf{B}^{(\tau)} = [\mathbf{act}_1, \mathbf{act}_2, \dots, \mathbf{act}_k]$ during planning iteration τ .

For a batch-targeting node n_ℓ , constraint validation ensures:

$$\mathbf{u}_\ell + \sum_{\mathbf{act} \in \mathbf{B}^{(\tau)}} \frac{\mathbf{d}_{\mathbf{act}}}{\mathbf{r}_\ell} \leq \mathbf{1}, \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{d}_{\mathbf{act}}$ is the service demand vector from Eq. 4 for the service targeted by action \mathbf{act} .

The LLM determines adaptive batch size $k^{(\tau)}$ based on the logical coherence of the action sequence during strategic reasoning. When the LLM identifies strongly connected action dependencies (e.g., migrate-then-low-power for the final service on a node), it generates larger batches $k^{(\tau)} \rightarrow k_{\text{max}}$. Conversely, for independent actions or uncertain logical connections, the LLM selects conservative single-action batches $k^{(\tau)} = 1$.

b: Atomic Three-Tier State Management

During multi-step planning cycles, LLMs often struggle to identify which specific actions caused constraint violations and to adjust subsequent planning accordingly. This degrades decision quality between iterations. AgentEdge addresses this through explicit state management that maintains three concurrent state snapshots, providing clear context that significantly improves planning step quality:

$$\mathcal{T} = \{\mathbf{S}_{\text{baseline}}, \mathbf{S}_{\text{accepted}}, \mathbf{S}_{\text{simulated}}\}, \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{S}_{\text{baseline}}$ is the immutable initial state before planning, $\mathbf{S}_{\text{accepted}}$ contains validated actions, and $\mathbf{S}_{\text{simulated}}$ represents the tentative state for evaluation.

State transitions follow atomic semantics during each planning iteration:

$$\mathbf{S}_{\text{simulated}}^{(\tau)} = f_{\text{simulate}}(\mathbf{S}_{\text{accepted}}, \mathbf{B}^{(\tau)}). \quad (23)$$

LLM reasoning operates exclusively on $\mathbf{S}_{\text{accepted}}$ for input consistency, while action batches undergo validation

FIGURE 3. Planning Agent graph structure implementing ActSimCrit methodology with three-tier state management, strategic action batching, independent critic LLM evaluation, iterative rejection-feedback learning, and deadlock detection with resolution.

through $\mathbf{S}_{simulated}^{(\tau)}$. Upon validation, successful batches promote $\mathbf{S}_{accepted} \leftarrow \mathbf{S}_{simulated}^{(\tau)}$, while failed batches are discarded and added to $\mathcal{X}^{(\tau+1)}$, eliminating state corruption while enabling iterative convergence to valid solutions.

c: Iterative Rejection-Feedback Learning

When action batches violate constraints during simulation, the Planning Agent needs to understand why the rejection occurred to avoid repeating the same mistake. AgentEdge captures this by having the LLM generate structured rejection reasoning explaining which specific constraints were violated. The next planning iteration then uses the pre-simulation state combined with this rejection feedback, enabling the agent to adjust its strategy. This feedback mechanism significantly improves planning quality across iterations. During the planning iteration τ , when the action batch $\mathbf{B}^{(\tau)}$ violates capacity constraints in $\mathbf{S}_{simulated}$, the schema $\mathcal{V}_{i_{plan}}^{(\tau)}$ forces the LLM to generate structured rejection reasoning:

$$\text{Reject}^{(\tau)} = \mathbf{u}_\ell + \sum_{\text{act} \in \mathbf{B}^{(\tau)}} \frac{\mathbf{d}_{\text{act}}}{\mathbf{r}_\ell} > \mathbf{1}. \quad (24)$$

The rejection context accumulates failed batches with structured reasoning:

$$\mathcal{X}^{(\tau+1)} = \mathcal{X}^{(\tau)} \cup \{\mathbf{B}^{(\tau)}, \text{reason}^{(\tau)}\}. \quad (25)$$

The next planning iteration uses this context to avoid previous failures:

$$\mathbf{B}^{(\tau+1)} = f_{i_{plan}}(\mathcal{X}^{(\tau+1)}, \mathcal{V}_{i_{plan}}^{(\tau+1)}). \quad (26)$$

This creates a convergent planning cycle in which each iteration learns from the violations of structured constraints.

d: Deadlock Detection and Resolution

User requests may be infeasible when demanded resources exceed available infrastructure capacity or when conflicting constraints create impossible scenarios. Consider a scenario in which the service s_j is deployed on node n_A , while node n_B has only 1.0 core of the remaining capacity. A user request to “scale service s_j to 2.0 cores and move it to node n_B ” creates an unsatisfiable constraint since $d_j^c = 2.0$ exceeds the available capacity at n_B .

As a failsafe, the Planning Agent detects deadlock when no valid solution exists despite extensive planning iterations. Since checking all possible placements is computationally prohibitive, detection relies on iteration thresholds: deadlock is declared when both $\tau \geq \theta_{iter}$ (iteration threshold) and $|\mathcal{X}^{(\tau)}| \geq \theta_{reject}$ (rejection count) are exceeded. These thresholds scale with infrastructure size ($m, |\mathcal{S}|$) to balance detection sensitivity with computational cost.

When deadlock occurs, an LLM analyzes accumulated failures in $\mathcal{X}^{(\tau)}$ to propose an alternative request $\text{req}'(t)$ that may be achievable. The planning cycle resets and attempts this alternative. Future work could add human verification before accepting modified requests [26].

e: Computational Complexity Analysis

The Planning Agent dominates computational cost through iterative reasoning. Each LLM call incurs $\mathcal{O}(L^2)$ operations where L is the context length, due to the quadratic scaling of transformer attention [27], [28]. Context length L scales linearly with problem size: $L = \mathcal{O}(N)$ where $N = m + |\mathcal{S}|$ (nodes plus services), since prompts encode node utilizations ($\mathcal{O}(m)$ tokens), service configurations ($\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{S}|)$ tokens), and bounded execution history. Therefore, each LLM call costs $\mathcal{O}(L^2) = \mathcal{O}(N^2)$, and across τ iterations, total complexity is $\mathcal{O}(\tau \cdot N^2)$. This polynomial scaling vastly outperforms brute-force placement enumeration ($m^{|\mathcal{S}|}$ candidates).

f: Convergence Analysis

ActSimCrit is an iterative plan-validation loop. In this context, “convergence” means termination to either (i) a validated plan yielding a feasible placement, or (ii) an explicit deadlock report for infeasible requests.

Termination is enforced through dynamic structured outputs: at each iteration, the schema constrains the LLM to select only from placements satisfying current constraints, while rejected placements are excluded from the selection set $\Omega_{valid}(t)$. Since the placement space is finite and each failure removes options, the algorithm must eventually succeed or trigger explicit stopping criteria. This guarantee rests on three properties:

Property 1: Finite Placement Space. With m nodes and $|\mathcal{S}|$ services, the set of all possible placements $\Pi = \{\pi : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{N}\}$ is finite with $|\Pi| = m^{|\mathcal{S}|}$.

Property 2: Monotonic Rejection Accumulation. The rejection context $\mathcal{X}^{(\tau)}$ grows monotonically: $|\mathcal{X}^{(\tau+1)}| \geq |\mathcal{X}^{(\tau)}|$. Each rejected placement is added to the context and excluded from future selection via schema constraints.

Property 3: Explicit Stopping Criteria. Deadlock thresholds θ_{iter} and θ_{reject} halt the loop when both $\tau \geq \theta_{\text{iter}}$ and $|\mathcal{X}^{(\tau)}| \geq \theta_{\text{reject}}$, triggering deadlock resolution instead of indefinite retrying.

4) INFRASTRUCTURE ACTION AGENT SUBGRAPH

The Infrastructure Action Agent executes the orchestration plan delivered by the Planning Agent through sequential API calls to the infrastructure. The agent operates as a script executor that translates the validated placement π^* into concrete API operations (deployment, migration, scaling, power management):

$$\text{Execute}(\pi^*) = f_{i_{\text{act}}}(\pi^*, \mathcal{V}_{i_{\text{act}}}), \quad (27)$$

where $\mathcal{V}_{i_{\text{act}}}$ is the validation schema from Eq. 7 containing valid API operations for the current infrastructure state.

If an API call fails during execution, the Infrastructure Action Agent transitions from script executor to single-agent problem solver, autonomously diagnosing the failure and attempting recovery actions.

B. PARES: A FRAMEWORK FOR AGENT CAPABILITIES

PARES (Perceive, Act, Reason, Evaluate, Sustain) provides a capability framework for autonomous agents derived from analysis of existing frameworks [29]–[34]. For any autonomous agent a_i , PARES defines five fundamental capabilities:

$$\begin{aligned} P_i(\mathbf{o}_i(t)) &: \text{Perceive environment state} \\ A_i(\mathbf{T}_i) &: \text{Act through tools} \\ R_i(\mathbf{s}_i) &: \text{Reason with internal state} \\ E_i(\mathbf{m}_i) &: \text{Evaluate} \\ S_i(f_i) &: \text{Sustain memory.} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

PARES is derived from analyzing existing agentic frameworks in the machine learning literature [29]–[34]. The five capabilities (Perceive, Act, Reason, Evaluate, Sustain) emerged as the common constructs that distinguish autonomous agents from simple scripts: observing environment state, executing actions through tools, reasoning about decisions, evaluating outcomes, and maintaining context across interactions.

AgentEdge’s four agent roles (Intent, Observe, Plan, Act) derive from the sense-plan-act paradigm augmented with intent interpretation. The ordering Intent \rightarrow Observe \rightarrow Plan \rightarrow Act is grounded in the Belief-Desire-Intention (BDI) architecture [35]: intentions must precede action because they bound rational reasoning and

FIGURE 4. Agentic Spectrum positioning of AgentEdge’s four specialized agents based on PARES capability sophistication, with Planning Agent exhibiting highest complexity and Infrastructure Action Agent implementing basic capabilities.

prevent resource-limited agents from reasoning indefinitely. Multi-agent coordination research [36] further demonstrates that sharing intentions (future plans) outperforms sharing observations for coordination, because intent captures future behavior enabling proactive rather than reactive coordination.

The Agentic Spectrum provides a qualitative framework for positioning agents based on their PARES implementation sophistication. Fig. 4 shows how AgentEdge’s four agents span this spectrum. The Planning Agent exhibits the highest sophistication through ActSimCrit methodology, requiring extensive reasoning (R_i), multi-step memory (S_i), complex tool coordination (A_i), and comprehensive state perception (P_i), while the Infrastructure Action Agent implements basic PARES capabilities with minimal LLM interactions for direct API execution. The Intent and Observability Agents occupy intermediate positions, balancing specialized processing with moderate reasoning requirements.

C. DYNAMIC STRUCTURED OUTPUTS

LLMs can make mistakes when choosing orchestration actions, potentially attempting impossible actions like deploying a service to an already full server. AgentEdge prevents these errors by limiting the LLM’s choices to only valid options.

Consider three sets of possible actions:

- Ω_{all} : All possible actions (including impossible ones)
- $\Omega_{\text{valid}}(t)$: Only feasible actions at time t
- $\Omega_{\text{optimal}}(t)$: The best feasible actions at time t

where $\Omega_{\text{optimal}}(t) \subseteq \Omega_{\text{valid}}(t) \subset \Omega_{\text{all}}$.

Without schema validation, the LLM can choose any action from Ω_{all} . The probability of making an error (choosing an infeasible action) is:

$$P_{\text{error}}^{\text{unconstrained}} = 1 - \frac{|\Omega_{\text{valid}}(t)|}{|\Omega_{\text{all}}|}. \quad (29)$$

This probability is high because most random placements violate capacity constraints from Eq. 5.

In contrast, with schema validation, AgentEdge restricts the LLM to choose only from $\Omega_{valid}(t)$. Now the error probability becomes:

$$P_{error}^{constrained} = 1 - \frac{|\Omega_{optimal}(t)|}{|\Omega_{valid}(t)|}. \quad (30)$$

Quantitatively, the improvement in error probability is:

$$\Delta P_{error} = P_{error}^{unconstrained} - P_{error}^{constrained} > 0. \quad (31)$$

This improvement occurs because we eliminate all impossible actions while retaining all good actions, significantly reducing the chance of orchestration failures. These structured outputs become particularly important when organizing LLMs into distributed reasoning networks.

D. DISTRIBUTED REASONING DECOMPOSITION

The benefits of distributing reasoning across specialized agents can be quantified mathematically. Research confirms that LLMs achieve significantly better performance when complex reasoning is decomposed into intermediate steps rather than attempted monolithically [37].

For mathematical analysis, let:

- $p \in (0, 1]$: baseline accuracy for focused single-step tasks
- $\beta \in (0, 1)$: accuracy loss per step interaction
- η : number of required sequential reasoning steps.

When a single LLM attempts all steps, accuracy degrades due to task complexity. This yields a success probability:

$$P_{monolithic} = p^\eta \cdot (1 - \beta)^{\eta(\eta-1)}. \quad (32)$$

In contrast, AgentEdge decomposes reasoning between specialized nodes. Each node maintains the baseline accuracy p for its designated step:

$$P_{distributed} = p^\eta. \quad (33)$$

The improvement factor $P_{distributed}/P_{monolithic} = 1/(1 - \beta)^{\eta(\eta-1)}$ grows superexponentially with complexity η , providing mathematical justification for AgentEdge’s hierarchical multi-agent graph-of-graphs architecture.

V. EVALUATION

This section presents: (i) the experimental setup with scenarios and simulation, (ii) model selection across five LLMs, (iii) baseline comparison against generic agentic frameworks, (iv) digital twin effectiveness through ablation studies, and (v) energy optimization scalability across infrastructure sizes.

A. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup consists of three components. First, we design six representative orchestration scenarios that test reasoning under resource conflicts and energy optimization at scale. Second, we develop a custom edge-cloud simulator implementing the infrastructure model from Section III to create reproducible test conditions. Third, we establish evaluation metrics measuring success rate, response time, API efficiency, and energy reduction.

1) ORCHESTRATION SCENARIOS

Production orchestration must handle three challenges simultaneously, as failure in any one causes system-wide degradation [3]. First, resource conflicts occur when new deployments exceed available capacity. Second, conflicting requirements arise where optimization objectives contradict each other. Third, scalability challenges emerge across heterogeneous infrastructure tiers. We designed six scenarios that systematically test these challenges, exposing critical failure modes of traditional orchestration approaches.

a: Constraint Resolution Scenarios (1-3)

These scenarios test multi-step reasoning under resource conflicts that cannot be resolved through simple greedy allocation.

Scenario 1: Full Node. This scenario evaluates basic constraint handling. Deploying a 2-core service on a fully-utilized 4-core node requires migrating existing services first. This tests fundamental planning capabilities and service migration coordination.

Scenario 2: Low-Power Conflict. This scenario introduces conflicting objectives. The user requests to simultaneously put edge-1 in low-power mode while scaling APIService (currently hosted on edge-1) to 1.4 cores. Since services cannot run on low-power nodes, the agent must migrate APIService to edge-0 before executing the power transition. This tests dependency detection and coordinated migration-scaling-power management across multiple nodes.

Scenario 3: Compound Constraint. This scenario creates an intentional deadlock to test AgentEdge’s deadlock detection and resolution mechanism from Section IV. The user requests to put edge-1 in low-power mode while scaling APIService to 2.4 cores. However, migrating both services from edge-1 to edge-0 would exceed edge-0’s available capacity, creating an unsatisfiable constraint.

b: Energy Optimization Scenarios (4-6)

These scenarios evaluate scalability across infrastructure sizes that span typical edge deployments (8 nodes), mid-sized installations (18 nodes), and large-scale edge deployments (35 nodes). All scenarios start from energy-inefficient configurations with underutilized services

spread across nodes, leaving idle nodes consuming baseline power.

Agents must consolidate services onto fewer nodes and transition idle nodes to low-power mode. This progression tests whether multi-agent coordination maintains effectiveness as infrastructure complexity increases and whether planning overhead causes performance degradation at scale.

2) INFRASTRUCTURE SIMULATOR

Evaluating agent reasoning quality requires deterministic ground truth for decision correctness. Simulation provides this by isolating agent decision-making as the independent variable while maintaining realistic resource constraints [6], [38]. This methodology aligns with established practice in agentic AI research, where interaction in physical environments is expensive and sometimes infeasible. A more commonly adopted approach is to develop agent skillsets and behavioral policies in virtual worlds before deploying in physical environments [13]. The digital twin simulator serves this purpose: it provides a controlled environment where agent reasoning can be validated without risking production infrastructure, enabling systematic evaluation of constraint satisfaction, energy optimization, and multi-step planning.

The simulator employs a Flask-based API architecture, implementing the heterogeneous infrastructure model $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{E})$ from Section III with detailed resource management and energy tracking per Eq. 3. The implementation includes 12 distinct API endpoints, continuous power monitoring at 5s intervals, 60% low-power mode energy reduction, and stochastic operation timing reflecting real-world constraints. Table 4 details the technical specifications covering three-tier hierarchical infrastructure, differentiated service types with resource requirements \mathbf{d}_j , network communication patterns, energy consumption models per Eq. 3, and stochastic operation timing.

3) EVALUATION METRICS & REPRODUCIBILITY

We employ four primary metrics: success rate $S = n_{success}/n_{runs}$ measuring task completion through exact end-state matching, response time $T_{response}$ quantifying total orchestration latency, API efficiency A_{calls} tracking infrastructure queries per run, and energy reduction $E_{reduction}$ measuring power consumption savings. For the energy-optimization scenarios in Section V.E, we also report four complementary measures to give deeper insight into orchestration outcome quality beyond exact end-state matching: energy gain, target shortfall, final-state constraint-violation counts, and action counts. Energy gain quantifies the percentage reduction relative to the initial energy state. Target shortfall quantifies

how close a generated plan comes to the scenario-defined low-power target by measuring the share of services that would still require one additional migration. Final-state constraint-violation counts report remaining CPU-overflow nodes, memory-overflow nodes, low-power nodes that still host services, and empty online nodes. Action counts report successful migrations, low-power transitions, and scaling actions per run.

The success determination follows an end-state matching protocol. Each scenario pre-defines multiple valid target placements $\Pi_{target} = \{\pi_1^*, \dots, \pi_\nu^*\}$. Each $\pi_\kappa^* : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ represents an acceptable orchestration outcome conforming to capacity constraints from Eq. 5. The evaluation requires the final agent-generated placement π_{final} to match exactly at least one target: $\pi_{final} \in \Pi_{target}$.

Statistical analysis of binary success rates employs the Wilson score method [39], which provides superior confidence interval properties compared to normal approximation and prevents intervals from exceeding [0,1] bounds for extreme success rate proportions.

For experimental rigor, we execute 60 runs per model/system (20 per scenario) for model selection and baseline comparison, 60 per condition for digital twin ablation studies, and 10 per scenario for energy optimization, totaling 630 runs across all phases. Deterministic seeding follows SHA256(phase, model, scenario, iteration) to ensure consistent randomness across all evaluations.

All experiments run on a Linux host with Python 3.13+ and fixed API timeouts to ensure consistent evaluation conditions. LLM inference was accessed through a hosted provider. The agentic orchestration framework utilizes LangGraph for workflow management, with structured output extraction handled by Instructor and Pydantic for type-safe validation. With the experimental foundation established, we proceed to systematic model selection.

B. MODEL SELECTION

Model selection directly determines whether multi-agent orchestration succeeds or fails in production. Orchestration demands simultaneous capabilities in tool coordination, mathematical reasoning for resource constraints, and multi-step planning under real-time requirements. This evaluation determines which foundation model enables reliable autonomous service management.

We benchmark five state-of-the-art open-source LLMs: `kimi-k2-1T` [40], `qwen3-235B` [41], `deepseek-r1-70B` [42], `llama-4-109B` [43], and `gpt-oss-120B` [44] across all six orchestration scenarios. The evaluation identifies which model best balances reasoning capability, execution speed, and cost-efficiency for autonomous service management.

TABLE 3. Six orchestration evaluation scenarios testing constraint resolution (Full Node, Low-Power Conflict, Compound Constraint) and scalable energy optimization (Small: 8 nodes, Medium: 18 nodes, Large: 35 nodes) with quantitative success metrics

#	Scenario	Infrastructure State	Orchestration Challenge	Success Metric
1	Full Node	edge-0: 100% util. (WA+DB+API) edge-1: 0% util. (idle)	Deploy service on full node: must migrate existing services first	≥ 2.0 cores freed via migration
2	Low-Power Conflict	edge-0: 24% util. (MWA+Mon) edge-1: 10% util. (DB+API)	Scale API to 1.4 cores while putting edge-1 in low-power mode	Migration-first strategy execution
3	Compound Constraint	edge-0: 48% util. (MWA+Mon) edge-1: 10% util. (DB+API)	Scale API to 2.4 cores while powering down edge-1: creates 0.52-core deficit	Creative redistribution or partial scaling
4	Energy: Small	6 services 8 nodes 2 idle	Consolidate services, power down idle nodes	Energy reduction >0 W
5	Energy: Medium	15 services 18 nodes 3 idle	Consolidate services, power down idle nodes	Energy reduction >0 W
6	Energy: Large	30 services 35 nodes 6 idle	Consolidate services, power down idle nodes	Energy reduction >0 W

Note: Infrastructure State reflects CPU utilization percentages based on allocated/total cores per node. Service Abbreviations: MWA=MainWebApp, Mon=Monitoring, DB=DatabaseService, API=APIService, WA=WebApp. Success Metrics define quantitative criteria for orchestration success evaluation.

1) MODEL OVERVIEW

Table 5 presents a detailed comparison of the evaluated models across key architectural and performance metrics. The model selection process implements systematic prefiltering from the broader LLM marketplace, ensuring compliance with essential requirements: open-source availability, function calling capabilities, mathematical reasoning proficiency, and programming competence.

The selected models offer diverse capabilities including agent-centric design with tool integration (*kimi-k2-1T*), mathematical reasoning with dual thinking modes (*qwen3-235B*), systematic algorithmic reasoning (*deepseek-r1-70B*), long-context multimodal processing (*llama-4-109B*), and production-scale agentic capabilities (*gpt-oss-120B*), ensuring comprehensive evaluation across key dimensions required for effective orchestration: tool coordination, logical reasoning, systematic planning, and complex scenario analysis.

2) SPEED-COST-INTELLIGENCE TRADE-OFFS

Fig. 5 illustrates the speed-cost-intelligence trade-offs. The analysis shows theoretical inference speeds as

reported by providers [45] and associated costs. Models include *deepseek-r1-70B* (1501.0 tokens/s, \$0.05/M tokens), *gpt-oss-120B* (2870.6 tokens/s), *llama-4-109B* (2724.6 tokens/s), *qwen3-235B* (1509.8 tokens/s, \$0.247/M tokens), and *kimi-k2-1T* (466.1 tokens/s, \$0.727/M tokens). These models exhibit varying intelligence indices as measured by standardized benchmarks [45]. This three-dimensional optimization necessitates comprehensive orchestration performance evaluation to identify the optimal model.

3) END STATE MATCHING

Orchestration success requires achieving correct infrastructure end states that satisfy all constraints. Unlike creative tasks, orchestration has objectively correct and incorrect outcomes.

Qwen3-235B achieves 78.3% success rate, significantly outperforming *kimi-k2-1T* (71.7%), *deepseek-r1-70B* (48.3%), *gpt-oss-120B* (40.0%), and *llama-4-109B* (23.3%) (Fig. 6). More than half of state-of-the-art LLMs fail in over 50% of orchestration scenarios despite strong performance on traditional NLP benchmarks,

TABLE 4. Infrastructure simulator specifications spanning three-tier deployment with heterogeneous resources, stochastic operation timing, power modeling, network latency, and real-time constraint validation

Infrastructure Component	Far Edge Tier	Near Edge Tier	Cloud Tier
Node Count	2–24	0–10	0–1
CPU Cores	4.0	16.0	64.0
Memory (GB)	8.0	32.0	256.0
Far Edge-to-Near Edge Latency	10 ms to 25 ms	—	—
Near Edge-to-Cloud Latency	—	25 ms to 60 ms	—
Power Consumption (W)	10–35	40–120	180–450
Low-Power Mode Reduction	60%	60%	60%
Web Service Resources	0.25 cores, 0.128 GB memory		
Database Resources	0.5 cores, 0.256 GB memory		
API Service Resources	0.25 cores, 0.128 GB memory		
Deployment Timing	15 s to 45 s web/api, 45 s to 120 s database		
Migration Timing	8 s to 30 s base + data transfer		
Scaling Timing	Up: 6 s to 54 s, Down: 5 s to 32 s		
Stochastic Timing Variance	Deploy: $\pm 25\%$, Migrate: $\pm 20\%$, Scale: $\pm 15\%$, Status: $\pm 10\%$		
Network Latency Fluctuations	± 1 ms to 2 ms random variations per 5 s interval		
Service Metrics Variations	Latency: ± 5 ms, Throughput: ± 10 RPS, Error: 0–5%		
Failure Rate Modeling	Probabilistic distributions: 0.1–2.0% operation failure		
Power Sampling	5 s intervals with utilization-based fluctuations		
Energy Model	Utilization-based (60% cores, 30% memory, 10% storage)		
Resource Validation	Real-time constraint checking		

TABLE 5. Five open-source LLM candidates with parameters ranging from 70B to 1T (32B-235B active), context windows of 128K-1M+ tokens, spanning Mixture of Experts (MoE) Transformer and Dense Transformer architectures (Q4 2024-Q2 2025 releases), all supporting function calling, mathematical reasoning, and code generation

#	Model	Params	Context	Architecture	Release	Open-source	Tools	Math	Code
1	kimi-k2-1T	1T/32B	128K	MoE Transform.	Q4 2024	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	qwen3-235B	235B/22B	128K	MoE Transform.	Q1 2025	✓	✓	✓	✓
3	deepseek-r1-70B	70B	131K	Dense Transform.	Q1 2025	✓	✓	✓	✓
4	llama-4-109B	109B/17B	1M+	MoE Multimodal	Q2 2025	✓	✓	✓	✓
5	gpt-oss-120B	117B/5.1B	131K	MoE Transform.	Q1 2025	✓	✓	✓	✓

FIGURE 5. Speed-cost-intelligence trade-offs for five candidate LLMs ranging from 466.1 tokens/s (kimi-k2-1T) to 2870.6 tokens/s (gpt-oss-120B) with pricing from \$0.05/M to \$0.727/M tokens, evaluated against standardized intelligence benchmarks.

FIGURE 6. Orchestration success rates across six scenarios with qwen3-235B achieving 78.3% (best), significantly outperforming kimi-k2-1T (71.7%), deepseek-r1-70B (48.3%), gpt-oss-120B (40.0%), and llama-4-109B (23.3%) using exact end-state matching validation.

demonstrating that benchmark performance does not predict service orchestration capability and necessitating domain-specific evaluation.

4) TOTAL AGENT RUNTIME

Production orchestration must respond within acceptable latency bounds to handle dynamic infrastructure changes. The question is whether reasoning quality comes at prohibitive time costs.

Qwen3-235B achieves 45.9s response time while maintaining 78.3% success (Fig. 7). In contrast, deepseek-r1-70B completes fastest (29.2s) but achieves only 48.3% success. Meanwhile, llama-4-109B requires 77.4s yet fails 76.7% of scenarios. Orchestration latency correlates more with reasoning quality than raw inference speed. Failed attempts and retry loops dominate total runtime, not LLM token generation.

FIGURE 7. Total agent runtime showing qwen3-235B achieving optimal speed-accuracy balance at 45.9s with 78.3% success, while deepseek-r1-70B completes fastest (29.2s) but achieves only 48.3% success, and llama-4-109B requires 77.4s yet fails 76.7% of scenarios.

Beyond aggregate metrics, we examine model performance across individual scenario types to identify capability gaps.

5) SCENARIO COMPLEXITY

Aggregate success rates may hide critical weaknesses in specific scenario types. The three constraint resolution scenarios test progressively complex reasoning: basic resource conflict (Full Node), dependency coordination (Low-Power Conflict), and deadlock resolution (Compound Constraint).

Qwen3-235B achieves balanced performance across all constraint types (100% on Full Node, 85% on Low-Power Conflict, 50% on Compound Constraint) (Fig. 8). Other models exhibit pronounced weaknesses. llama-4-109B fails completely on compound constraints (0%). deepseek-r1-70B shows inconsistent performance despite reasonable success on simpler scenarios. Orchestration requires robust general reasoning, not specialized optimization for particular scenario types. We select qwen3-235B for all subsequent experiments based on its consistent cross-scenario performance.

C. SINGLE-AGENT VS MULTI-AGENT

With the optimal LLM identified, we examine whether multi-agent specialization is necessary or generic single-agent frameworks can succeed in orchestration. Prior agentic frameworks excel in other domains but have never been evaluated for service orchestration, making this comparison critical to determine whether service orchestration demands specialized multi-agent coordination.

We compare against agentic AI frameworks (ReAct, LATS) that, like AgentEdge, interpret natural language intent and coordinate multi-step actions. Traditional optimization algorithms solve formally specified mathe-

FIGURE 8. Model performance heatmap across constraint resolution scenarios revealing qwen3-235B’s balanced capability (100% Full Node, 85% Low-Power Conflict, 50% Compound Constraint), while other models exhibit pronounced weaknesses (llama-4-109B: 0% compound constraints, deepseek-r1-70B: inconsistent performance across scenario types).

mathematical programs rather than translating intent into executable plans. As discussed in Section IV-A, such solvers can be invoked by the Planning Agent as optimization backends when beneficial.

We compare AgentEdge against two baseline agentic frameworks through 60 independent runs per system across constraint resolution scenarios (1-3) from Table 3. All systems use identical evaluation conditions with qwen3-235B as the base LLM and exact end-state matching for success measurement.

ReAct [6] synergizes reasoning and acting in language models through interleaved thought-action sequences. It increases the action space A with the language space L to create $\hat{A} = A \cup L$. The framework employs few-shot prompting with human-annotated trajectories.

LATS [19] represents the most advanced single-agent approach. It unifies reasoning, acting, and planning through Monte Carlo Tree Search. The framework implements six-operation cycles: selection, expansion, evaluation, simulation, backpropagation, and reflection. LATS leverages LLMs as agents, value functions, and optimizers simultaneously to improve decision-making.

AgentEdge achieves 78.3% success rate compared to ReAct’s 28.3% and LATS’s 65.0% (Fig. 9), representing 2.76 \times and 1.20 \times improvements respectively. Generic frameworks fail not due to LLM limitations (all use qwen3-235B), but due to architectural mismatch with infrastructure constraints. ReAct’s sequential reasoning lacks systematic planning for multi-step coordination required by orchestration scenarios. LATS’s tree search assumes state reversibility that does not exist in infrastructure, where deployed services cannot be “undeployed” to backtrack through decision trees. AgentEdge requires 46 seconds versus ReAct’s 9 seconds, yet this coordination overhead enables success where faster execution produces only faster failures. These empirical results align with the distributed reasoning decomposition analysis from

(a) Success Rate Comparison (b) Response Time Comparison

FIGURE 9. AgentEdge achieves 78.3% success rate versus ReAct’s 28.3% (2.76 \times improvement) and LATS’s 65.0% (1.20 \times improvement) across 60 independent runs per system, with 46s response time demonstrating that multi-agent coordination overhead enables reliable orchestration where faster generic frameworks produce faster failures.

Section IV, which suggests performance gains when decomposing complex reasoning across specialized agents.

The 2.76 \times improvement over state-of-the-art agentic frameworks establishes that orchestration requires specialized architectural design, not merely applying existing ML frameworks to infrastructure domains.

D. EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL TWIN

AgentEdge’s core innovation is ActSimCrit’s digital twin simulation, which validates orchestration plans before real execution. Through ablation comparing AgentEdge with (+DT) and without (-DT) simulation while keeping all other components identical, we demonstrate that simulation prevents catastrophic planning failures.

Without simulation, agents exhibit extreme variability with 8 to 517 API calls per run (standard deviation 109.4) (Fig. 10), while simulation enables stable performance with 10.9 ± 1.1 calls. This 10 \times reduction in variance prevents agents from entering infinite retry loops where they repeatedly propose invalid plans, query infrastructure for feedback, receive rejection, and retry without learning. The digital twin breaks this cycle by validating strategies before execution, enabling safe exploration of solution spaces.

Beyond stability, digital twin provides 1.47 \times success improvement (78.3% vs 53.3%).

E. ENERGY OPTIMIZATION SCALABILITY

Production edge-cloud deployments span from small installations (8 nodes) to large-scale edge deployments (35 nodes), where multi-agent coordination must maintain effectiveness as infrastructure complexity grows. We evaluate energy optimization across three infrastructure

FIGURE 10. Digital twin simulation effectiveness: ActSimCrit (+DT) achieves 78.3% success and stable 10.9±1.1 API calls versus 53.3% success and highly variable 37.7±109.4 API calls without simulation (-DT), demonstrating 1.47× success improvement and 10× variance reduction through digital twin validation.

FIGURE 11. Infrastructure scaling progression showing Small (8 nodes, 6 services), Medium (18 nodes, 15 services), and Large (35 nodes, 30 services) three-tier edge-cloud deployments with node and service distribution across far-edge, near-edge, and cloud tiers for energy optimization evaluation.

scales: Small (8 nodes, 6 services), Medium (18 nodes, 15 services), and Large (35 nodes, 30 services) (Fig. 11).

AgentEdge achieves power savings of 89 W (Small), 300.8 W (Medium), and 185.2 W (Large) (Fig. 12), showing that multi-agent coordination can still reduce power at the evaluated large scale. Response times grow non-linearly (223.7 s, 171.0 s, 687.6 s), with the medium-scale scenario showing the most favorable balance between planning overhead and energy-saving opportunity.

To complement the aggregate energy results, Fig. 13 reports three rows of additional measures for the evaluated small, medium, and large-scale energy-optimization cases. Row 1 shows energy gain and target shortfall. We use target shortfall to evaluate how close the generated

plans come to the scenario-defined target state. We measure target shortfall as service-relocation shortfall from the scenario-defined initial placements, the logged successful migrations, and the final node states. Service-relocation shortfall is the percentage of services that would still require one additional migration to reach the scenario-defined low-power target. Row 2 shows counts of final-state constraint violations together with successful migrations and low-power transitions per run. Scaling actions are reported separately and remain zero. Row 3 shows response time and total token usage across the evaluated node and service regimes.

The results reveal three main patterns. First, the hard constraints are satisfied across all three scales: CPU and memory overflows stay at zero, and low-power nodes that still host services are rare. Second, the medium-scale case provides the best trade-off because it achieves the largest energy gain while keeping target shortfall moderate. Third, target shortfall rises with scenario complexity and reaches its highest level in the large-scale case, which also has the lowest energy gain. It often stops in under-consolidated states and leaves more empty nodes online.

Planning latency and token usage are the main bottleneck of the current LLM-driven planning implementation. The third row of Fig. 13 shows the measured planning cost across the evaluated 8/18/35-node and 6/15/30-service scales. Response time indicates the wall-clock delay before a plan is available for execution. Total token usage indicates the LLM computation cost of generating that plan. Energy gain indicates the achieved consolidation benefit, while target shortfall indicates how far the final placement still remains from the scenario-defined target. Across the three evaluated scales, the large-scale case has the highest mean response time (687.6 s). Mean total token usage is much higher for the medium- and large-scale cases than for the small-scale case (0.59M, 5.27M, and 4.82M tokens). Taken together, these results show two scale effects. First, moving from the small-scale case to the medium- and large-scale cases sharply increases planning cost. Second, moving from the medium-scale case to the large-scale case does not produce a proportional token increase. Instead, in the evaluated S6 large-scale scenario, the current planner reaches its highest response time while also showing the lowest energy gain and the highest target shortfall. In that large-scale case, many services still sit on online nodes that should have been consolidated even after an expensive planning process. The Planning Agent remains responsible for more than 99% of total token usage. However, the framework can also integrate heuristic or exact planning algorithms as external tools, allowing the Planning Agent to reason over which tools to invoke and the quality of the generated plans based on runtime and solution-quality trade-offs.

FIGURE 12. Energy optimization achieving power savings of 89W (Small), 300.8W (Medium), and 185.2W (Large) through intelligent service consolidation and low-power mode transitions, with response times of 223.7s, 171.0s, and 687.6s respectively across small to large-scale deployments.

Digital twins span multiple timescales, including real-time control (milliseconds), operational planning (minutes to hours), and strategic optimization (hours to days) [46], [47]. In networking and cloud systems, digital twins predominantly support planning, validation, and optimization rather than fast control loops. Strategic orchestration tasks such as energy consolidation, capacity planning, and workload rebalancing typically execute during maintenance windows. The 687s planning time is acceptable when decisions remain in effect until the next cycle.

F. DISCUSSION

The current evaluation assumes reliable network connectivity. Four deployment considerations merit discussion.

Cost considerations. The Planning Agent dominates token usage (99%+) due to iterative ActSimCrit reasoning. Each orchestration request averages 1.2M input and 0.24M output tokens overall. The scale-specific total-token measurements are reported in Fig. 13. At qwen3-235B pricing (\$0.13/M input, \$0.60/M output), each request costs \$0.30, yielding \$11K annually at 100 requests/day. LLM inference prices have dropped 9–900× per year [48], improving cost viability. For cost-sensitive deployments, local hosting eliminates per-token costs, with the hardware investment recovering within 4–34 months depending on usage [49].

Scalability. AgentEdge’s graph-of-graphs architecture supports hierarchical partitioning for larger deployments. Regional orchestrators manage local clusters while a global coordinator handles cross-region decisions. Since planning dominates latency, regional orchestrators can operate in parallel.

Privacy requirements. The dynamic schema generation (Eq. 7) provides a natural extension point for

privacy constraints. Differential privacy mechanisms [50] could protect placement decisions in multi-tenant environments by adding calibrated noise to orchestration outputs.

Bandwidth constraints. The QoS penalty function (Eq. 11) captures latency $\ell(n_i, n_j)$. Extending to bandwidth-constrained environments would add an explicit term penalizing cross-node data movement. Recent work on clustered federated learning [50] demonstrates complementary multi-agent coordination techniques under bandwidth limits.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented AgentEdge, a distributed intelligence framework for the orchestration of 6G edge-cloud services. AgentEdge addresses the reliability limitations of generic agentic AI frameworks applied to orchestration domains through specialized multi-agent coordination. AgentEdge introduces the PARES (Perceive, Act, Reason, Evaluate, Sustain) framework establishing minimum capabilities for autonomous agent qualification. AgentEdge deploys specialized agents in four orchestration roles: intent processing, infrastructure monitoring, strategic planning, and action execution. Our key innovation, the ActSimCrit methodology, replaces direct infrastructure experimentation with digital twin simulation for safe strategy validation. The experimental evaluation demonstrates significant improvements over the baseline agentic frameworks. AgentEdge achieves 2.76× superior success rates compared to generic agentic frameworks (ReAct, LATS) and 10× reduction in API call variability, maintaining consistent performance (± 1.1 calls) versus variable baseline behaviors (± 109.4 standard deviation). Ablation analysis confirms ActSimCrit’s critical contribution with 1.47× success rate improvement over direct

FIGURE 13. Complementary measures for the evaluated small, medium, and large-scale energy-optimization cases. Row 1: energy gain and target shortfall (service-relocation shortfall). Row 2: counts of final-state constraint violations and successful migrations/low-power transitions per run. Row 3: response time and total token usage across the evaluated 8/18/35-node and 6/15/30-service regimes.

planning. Energy optimization shows significant power savings across 8 to 35 nodes, while the largest evaluated case exposes the current planning bottleneck.

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